

INTERVAL-VALUED PYTHAGOREAN FUZZY WEAK BI-HYPERIDEALS IN HYPERSEMIGROUPS

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ABSTRACT. In this paper we introduce the concept of interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup and interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals in hypersemigroups. We show that the $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ -level set of interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideal is a weak bi-hyperideal in hypersemigroup. We characterize cartesian product of interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy set and examine that the cartesian product of interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals is also an interval-valued Pythagorean weak bi-hyperideal in hypersemigroups.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fuzzy set and interval-valued fuzzy set were introduced by Zadeh[14, 15]. Atanassov[2, 3] introduced intuitionistic fuzzy set in 1986. Later he developed interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy set. In 2013 Yager[13] established Pythagorean fuzzy set theory. Kumar et al.[7] applied the concept of Pythagorean fuzzy set in decision making problem. Peng[9] extended the concept of Pythagorean fuzzy set to interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy set in 2019. He defined some operations on this set. Chen[4] introduced interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy outranking method in applications. Adak et al.[1] and Hussian et al.[6] applied interval-valued fuzzy set in ideals. Marty[8] extended algebraic structures to algebraic hyperstructures. The concept of hypersemigroup is a generalization of semigroup. In a classical algebraic structure the composition of two elements yields an element while in hyperstructures composition of two elements is a non empty set. Davvaz[5] studied fuzzy hyperideals and intuitionistic fuzzy hyperideals in hypersemigroups. Pibaljomme et al.[10] characterized fuzzy bi hyperideals in ordered semihypergroups and Subha et al.[12] studied fuzzy rough bi hyperideals in semihypergroups.

In this paper we introduce the concept of interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup and interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals in hypersemigroups. We show that union of two interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroups and interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals are also interval-valued Pythagorean

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fuzzy subsemihypergroups and interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals respectively. In the last section we discuss the cartesian product of two interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals in hypersemigroups.

2. PRELIMINARIES

In this section we recall some basic definitions such as hypersemigroup, interval-valued fuzzy set etc.

Definition 2.1. [5] Let \mathcal{T} be a non-empty universe set and $\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{T})$ is the collection of all subsets of \mathcal{T} . The hyperoperation \bullet on \mathcal{T} is defined by

$$\bullet : \mathcal{T} \times \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{T})$$

The set \mathcal{T} with the hyperoperation \bullet is called hypergroupoid (say \mathcal{T}^\bullet). For any $t_1, t_2 \in \mathcal{T}$, the image of $(t_1, t_2) \in \mathcal{T} \times \mathcal{T}$ is denoted by $t_1 \bullet t_2$.

Let \mathcal{T}_1 and \mathcal{T}_2 be the subsets of $\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{T})$ then the hyperoperation (\star) between \mathcal{T}_1 and \mathcal{T}_2 is defined by

$$\mathcal{T}_1 \star \mathcal{T}_2 = \bigcup_{(t_1, t_2) \in \mathcal{T}_1 \times \mathcal{T}_2} t_1 \bullet t_2 \quad (2.1)$$

where

$$\star : \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{T}) \times \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{T}) \rightarrow \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{T}).$$

Definition 2.2. [5] A hypergroupoid [11] (\mathcal{T}^\bullet) is called a hypersemigroup (say \mathcal{T}^\star) if $(\{c\} \star \{d\}) \star \{e\} = \{c\} \star (\{d\} \star \{e\})$ for all $c, d, e \in \mathcal{T}$.

Definition 2.3. [11] A subset S of \mathcal{T}^\star is said to be a subsemihypergroup if $S \star S \subseteq S$.

Definition 2.4. [9] Let \mathcal{T}^\star be a hypersemigroup and $D[0, 1]$ be a collection of sub intervals of $[0, 1]$. An interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy set $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M(x), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(x) \rangle$ is of the form $\mathcal{P} = \{ \langle x, [\tilde{\delta}_M^-(x), \tilde{\delta}_M^+(x)], [\tilde{\delta}_{NM}^-(x), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^+(x)] \rangle : 0 \leq \tilde{\delta}_M^+(x)^2 + \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^+(x)^2 \leq 1 \}$.

In short $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$

where

$$\tilde{\delta}_M : \mathcal{T}^\star \longrightarrow D[0, 1] \text{ and } \tilde{\delta}_{NM} : \mathcal{T}^\star \longrightarrow D[0, 1].$$

$\tilde{\delta}_M$ is a membership grade and $\tilde{\delta}_{NM}$ is a non-membership grade of $x \in \mathcal{T}$.

Definition 2.5. [9] Let $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \langle \tilde{\zeta}_M, \tilde{\zeta}_{NM} \rangle$ be any two interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy sets of \mathcal{T}^\star . Then

- (i) $\mathcal{P} \cup \mathcal{Q} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M \vee \tilde{\zeta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \wedge \tilde{\zeta}_{NM} \rangle$ is a union of \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{Q} and
- (ii) $\mathcal{P} \cap \mathcal{Q} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M \wedge \tilde{\zeta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \vee \tilde{\zeta}_{NM} \rangle$ is a intersection of \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{Q} .

3. INTERVAL-VALUED PYTHAGOREAN FUZZY SUBSEMIHYPERGROUP OF HYPERSEMIGROUPS

In this section we introduce the notion of interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup and study some properties of this structure.

Definition 3.1. An interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy set $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ of \mathcal{T}^\star is said to be an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup if for $f \in \mathcal{T}^\star$ we have

- (i) $\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} \leq \inf_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f)$ and
- (ii) $\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} \geq \sup_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f)$ for all $u, v \in \mathcal{T}^\star$.

Example 3.2. Let $\mathcal{T}^* = \{p, q, r, s, t\}$ be a hypersemigroup with the Cayley table:

•	p	q	r	s	t
p	$\{p, q\}$				
q	$\{p, q\}$				
r	$\{p, q\}$	$\{p, q\}$	$\{r\}$	$\{r\}$	$\{t\}$
s	$\{p, q\}$	$\{p, q\}$	$\{r\}$	$\{s\}$	$\{t\}$
t	$\{p, q\}$	$\{p, q\}$	$\{r\}$	$\{r\}$	$\{t\}$

Define an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy set \mathcal{P} as

\mathcal{P}	$\tilde{\delta}_M$	$\tilde{\delta}_{NM}$
p	$[0.7, 0.8]$	$[0.1, 0.2]$
q	$[0.4, 0.5]$	$[0.4, 0.5]$
r	$[0.3, 0.5]$	$[0.5, 0.6]$
s	$[0, 0.2]$	$[0.3, 0.5]$
t	$[0.3, 0.5]$	$[0.5, 0.6]$

Since $\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(p), \tilde{\delta}_M(r)\} = [0.3, 0.5]$ and $\inf_{p, q \in p^*r} \{\tilde{\delta}_M(p), \tilde{\delta}_M(q)\} = [0.4, 0.5]$ which implies that $\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(p), \tilde{\delta}_M(r)\} \leq \inf_{p, q \in p^*r} \{\tilde{\delta}_M(p), \tilde{\delta}_M(q)\}$

and also we have

$$\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(p), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(r)\} = [0.5, 0.6] \text{ and } \sup_{p, q \in p^*r} \{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(p), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(q)\} = [0.4, 0.5]$$

which implies that $\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(p), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(r)\} \geq \sup_{p, q \in p^*r} \{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(p), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(q)\}$.

Similarly these inequalities hold for all $p, q, r, s, t \in \mathcal{T}^*$.

Hence \mathcal{P} is an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup of \mathcal{T}^* .

Theorem 3.1. If $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \langle \tilde{\zeta}_M, \tilde{\zeta}_{NM} \rangle$ are any two interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroups of \mathcal{T}^* then $\mathcal{P} \cap \mathcal{Q}$ is also an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup of \mathcal{T}^* .

Proof. Consider for $f \in \mathcal{T}^*$

$$\begin{aligned} \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M \cap \tilde{\zeta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M \cap \tilde{\zeta}_M(v)\} &= \min\left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\zeta}_M(u)\}, \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(v), \tilde{\zeta}_M(v)\}\right\} \\ &= \min\left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\}, \min\{\tilde{\zeta}_M(u), \tilde{\zeta}_M(v)\}\right\} \\ &\leq \min\left\{\inf_{f \in u^*v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f), \inf_{f \in u^*v} \tilde{\zeta}_M(f)\right\} \\ &\leq \inf_{f \in u^*v} \left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(f), \tilde{\zeta}_M(f)\}\right\} \\ &\leq \inf_{f \in u^*v} \tilde{\delta}_M \cap \tilde{\zeta}_M(f) \quad \forall u, v \in \mathcal{T}^*. \end{aligned}$$

Now consider for $f \in \mathcal{T}^*$

$$\begin{aligned} \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \cap \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \cap \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v)\} &= \max\left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u)\}, \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v)\}\right\} \\ &= \max\left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\}, \max\{\tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v)\}\right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \max \left\{ \sup_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f), \sup_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f) \right\} \\
&\geq \sup_{f \in u \star v} \left\{ \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f)\} \right\} \\
&\geq \sup_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \cup \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f) \quad \forall u, v \in \mathcal{T}^*.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{P} \cap \mathcal{Q}$ is an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup \mathcal{T}^* . \square

Definition 3.3. Let $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ be an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy set in \mathcal{T}^* . For any $\tilde{\alpha} \in D[0, 1]$ and $\tilde{\beta} \in D[0, 1]$, we define $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ -level set of \mathcal{P} as

$$\mathcal{P}^{(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}}, \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}} \rangle$$

where $\tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}} = \{x \in \mathcal{T}^* : \tilde{\delta}_M(x) \geq \tilde{\alpha}\}$ and

$$\tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}} = \{x \in \mathcal{T}^* : \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(x) \leq \tilde{\beta}\} \text{ for all } x \in \mathcal{T}^*.$$

Theorem 3.2. Let $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ be an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy set of \mathcal{T}^* . For $\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \in D[0, 1]$, the $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ -level cut of $\mathcal{P}(\mathcal{P}^{(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})})$ is a subsemihypergroup then \mathcal{P} is an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup of \mathcal{T}^* .

Proof. Let $\tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ be a subsemihypergroup of \mathcal{T}^* then for $u, v \in \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ we have

$$u \star v \in \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}} \quad (3.1)$$

Suppose if $\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} \not\geq \inf_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f)$ then we have

$$\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} > \inf_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f).$$

Then there exists some $t_0 \in D[0, 1]$ such that

$$\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} > t_0 > \inf_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f). \text{ This implies that}$$

$$\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} > t_0 \text{ and } \inf_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f) < t_0.$$

$\implies \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} > t_0$ and $\tilde{\delta}_M(f) < t_0$ for $f \in u \star v$

$\implies u \star v \notin \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ and either $u \in \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ or $v \in \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}}$.

This is a contradiction to Equation (3.1). Hence $\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} \leq \inf_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f)$.

Now, Since $\tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}}$ is a subsemihypergroup then for $u, v \in \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}}$ we have

$$u \star v \in \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}} \quad (3.2)$$

Suppose if $\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} \not\leq \sup_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f)$ then we have

$$\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} < \sup_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f).$$

Then there exists some $t_1 \in D[0, 1]$ such that

$$\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} < t_1 < \sup_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f). \text{ This implies that}$$

$$\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} < t_1 \text{ and } \sup_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f) > t_1$$

$\implies \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} < t_1$ and $\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f) > t_1$ for $f \in u \star v$

$\implies u \star v \notin \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}}$ and either $u \in \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}}$ or $v \in \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}}$.

Which is a contradiction to Equation (3.2).

Hence $\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} \geq \sup_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f)$.

\square

4. INTERVAL-VALUED PYTHAGOREAN FUZZY WEAK BI-HYPERIDEALS OF HYPERSEMIGROUPS

In this section we introduce the concept of interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals of hypersemigroups.

Definition 4.1. A subset W of \mathcal{T}^* is said to be a weak bi-hyperideal if $W \star W \star W \subseteq W$.

Definition 4.2. An interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ is said to be an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideal of \mathcal{T}^* if for $f \in \mathcal{T}^*$ we have

- (i) $\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(a), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} \leq \inf_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f)$ and
 (ii) $\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} \geq \sup_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f)$ for all $a, u, v \in \mathcal{T}^*$.

Example 4.3. Let $\mathcal{T}^* = \{p, q, r, s, t\}$ be a hypersemigroup with Cayley table:

\bullet	x	y	z
x	$\{z\}$	$\{z\}$	$\{z\}$
y	$\{x, z\}$	$\{z\}$	$\{z\}$
z	$\{z\}$	$\{z\}$	$\{z\}$

Define an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy set \mathcal{P} as

\mathcal{P}	$\tilde{\delta}_M$	$\tilde{\delta}_{NM}$
x	$[0.7, 0.8]$	$[0.1, 0.2]$
y	$[0.5, 0.6]$	$[0.4, 0.6]$
z	$[0.9, 1]$	$[0.3, 0.5]$

By routine calculation we can easily check that \mathcal{P} is an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideal of \mathcal{T}^* .

Theorem 4.1. Let $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \langle \tilde{\zeta}_M, \tilde{\zeta}_{NM} \rangle$ be any two interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals of \mathcal{T}^* then $\mathcal{P} \cap \mathcal{Q}$ is also an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideal of \mathcal{T}^* .

Proof. Let $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \langle \tilde{\zeta}_M, \tilde{\zeta}_{NM} \rangle$ be two interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals of \mathcal{T}^* . Consider for $f \in \mathcal{T}^*$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M \cap \tilde{\zeta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M \cap \tilde{\zeta}_M(a), \tilde{\delta}_M \cap \tilde{\zeta}_M(v)\} \\
 &= \min\left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\zeta}_M(u)\}, \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(a), \tilde{\zeta}_M(a)\}, \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(v), \tilde{\zeta}_M(v)\}\right\} \\
 &= \min\left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(a), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\}, \min\{\tilde{\zeta}_M(u), \tilde{\zeta}_M(a), \tilde{\zeta}_M(v)\}\right\} \\
 &\leq \min\left\{\inf_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f), \inf_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\zeta}_M(f)\right\} \\
 &\leq \inf_{f \in u \star a \star v} \left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(f), \tilde{\zeta}_M(f)\}\right\} \\
 &\leq \inf_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M \cap \tilde{\zeta}_M(f) \quad \forall u, v \in \mathcal{T}^*.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now consider for $f \in \mathcal{T}^*$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \cap \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \cap \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \cap \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v)\} \\
&= \max\left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u)\}, \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(a)\}, \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v)\}\right\} \\
&= \max\left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\}, \max\{\tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v)\}\right\} \\
&\geq \max\left\{\sup_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f), \sup_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f)\right\} \\
&\geq \sup_{f \in u \star a \star v} \left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f)\}\right\} \\
&\geq \sup_{f \in u \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \cap \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f) \quad \forall u, v \in \mathcal{T}^*.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus $\mathcal{P} \cap \mathcal{Q}$ is an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideal of \mathcal{T}^* . \square

Theorem 4.2. Let $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ be an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy set of \mathcal{T}^* . For $\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta} \in D[0, 1]$, the $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ -level cut of \mathcal{P} is a weak bi-hyperideal of \mathcal{T}^* then \mathcal{P} is an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideal of \mathcal{T}^* .

Proof. Let $\tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ be a weak bi-hyperideal of \mathcal{T}^* . By Theorem 3.2 \mathcal{P} is an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup. Then for $a, u, v \in \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ we have

$$u \star a \star v \in \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}} \quad (4.1)$$

Suppose if $\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(a), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} \not\geq \inf_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f)$ then we have

$$\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(a), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} > \inf_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f).$$

Then there exists some $t_\phi \in D[0, 1]$ such that

$$\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(a), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} > t_\phi > \inf_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f). \text{ This implies that}$$

$$\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(a), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} > t_\phi \text{ and } \inf_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f) < t_\phi.$$

$$\implies \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(a), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} > t_\phi \text{ and } \tilde{\delta}_M(f) < t_\phi \text{ for } f \in u \star a \star v$$

$$\implies u \star a \star v \notin \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}} \text{ and either } u \in \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}} \text{ or } a \in \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}} \text{ or } v \in \tilde{\delta}_M^{\tilde{\alpha}}.$$

This is a contradiction to Equation (4.1).

$$\text{Hence } \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u), \tilde{\delta}_M(a), \tilde{\delta}_M(v)\} \leq \inf_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_M(f).$$

Now, since $\tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}}$ is a weak bi-hyperideal then for $a, u, v \in \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}}$ we have

$$u \star a \star v \in \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}} \quad (4.2)$$

Suppose if $\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} \not\leq \sup_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f)$ then we have

$$\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} < \sup_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f).$$

Then there exists some $t_\xi \in D[0, 1]$ such that

$$\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} < t_\xi < \sup_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f). \text{ This implies that}$$

$$\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} < t_\xi \text{ and } \sup_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f) > t_\xi$$

$$\implies \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} < t_\xi \text{ and } \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f) > t_\xi \text{ for } f \in u \star a \star v$$

$$\implies u \star a \star v \notin \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}} \text{ and either } u \in \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}} \text{ or } a \in \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}} \text{ or } v \in \tilde{\delta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}}.$$

This is a contradiction to Equation (4.2).

$$\text{Hence } \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v)\} \geq \sup_{f \in u \star a \star v} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f).$$

\square

5. CARTESIAN PRODUCT OF INTERVAL-VALUED PYTHAGOREAN FUZZY WEAK BI-HYPERIDEALS IN HYPERSEMIGROUPS

In this section we discuss some properties of cartesian product of interval-valued fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals in hypersemigroups.

Definition 5.1. Let \mathcal{T}^* be a hypersemigroup. The cartesian product of two interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy sets $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \langle \tilde{\zeta}_M, \tilde{\zeta}_{NM} \rangle$ is denoted by $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$ and is defined by

$$\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q} = \{ \langle (p, q) / (\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(p, q), \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(p, q)) \rangle \text{ for all } (p, q) \in \mathcal{T}^* \times \mathcal{T}^* \}$$

Where $\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(p, q) = \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(p), \tilde{\zeta}_M(q)\}$,

$$\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(p, q) = \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(p), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(q)\} \text{ for all } (p, q) \in \mathcal{T}^* \times \mathcal{T}^*.$$

Example 5.2. Let us define two interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy sets $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \langle \tilde{\zeta}_M, \tilde{\zeta}_{NM} \rangle$ as follows:

\mathcal{P}	$\tilde{\delta}_M$	$\tilde{\delta}_{NM}$
c	[0.7, 0.8]	[0.3, 0.4]
d	[0.6, 0.9]	[0.1, 0.2]
e	[0, 0.2]	[0, 0.1]

\mathcal{Q}	$\tilde{\zeta}_M$	$\tilde{\zeta}_{NM}$
c	[0.4, 0.8]	[0.3, 0.4]
d	[0.6, 0.9]	[0.3, 0.4]
e	[0.4, 0.6]	[0.5, 0.7]

Then $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q} = \langle c / ([0.4, 0.8], [0.3, 0.4]), d / ([0.6, 0.9], [0.3, 0.4]), e / ([0.4, 0.6], [0, 0.7]) \rangle$.

Theorem 5.1. Let \mathcal{T}^* be a hypersemigroup. If interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy sets $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \langle \tilde{\zeta}_M, \tilde{\zeta}_{NM} \rangle$ are interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals of \mathcal{T}^* then $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$ is also an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy bi-hyperideal of $\mathcal{T}^* \times \mathcal{T}^*$.

Proof. Let \mathcal{P} and \mathcal{Q} are interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals of \mathcal{T}^* .

Consider for $(u_1, u_2), (v_1, v_2), (f_1, f_2) \in \mathcal{T}^* \times \mathcal{T}^*$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(u_1, u_2), \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(v_1, v_2)\} \\ &= \min\left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u_1), \tilde{\zeta}_M(u_2)\}, \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(v_1), \tilde{\zeta}_M(v_2)\}\right\} \\ &= \min\left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u_1), \tilde{\delta}_M(v_1)\}, \min\{\tilde{\zeta}_M(u_2), \tilde{\zeta}_M(v_2)\}\right\} \\ &\leq \min\left\{\inf_{f_1 \in u_1 v_1} \tilde{\delta}_M(f_1), \sup_{f_2 \in u_2 v_2} \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_2)\right\} \\ &\leq \inf_{\substack{f_1 \in u_1 v_1, \\ f_2 \in u_2 v_2}} \left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(f_1), \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_2)\}\right\} \\ &\leq \inf_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1 v_1, u_2 v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_1, f_2) \\ &\leq \inf_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_1, f_2), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u_1, u_2), \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v_1, v_2)\} \\
&= \max\left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u_2)\}, \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v_2)\}\right\} \\
&= \max\left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u_1), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v_1)\}, \max\{\tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u_2), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v_2)\}\right\} \\
&\geq \max\left\{\sup_{f_1 \in u_1 v_1} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f_1), \sup_{f_2 \in u_2 v_2} \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_2)\right\} \\
&\geq \sup_{\substack{f_1 \in u_1 v_1, \\ f_2 \in u_2 v_2}} \left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_2)\}\right\} \\
&\geq \sup_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1 v_1, u_2 v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_1, f_2) \\
&\geq \sup_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_1, f_2)
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$ is an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup of $\mathcal{T}^* \times \mathcal{T}^*$.

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(u_1, u_2), \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(a_1, a_2), \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(v_1, v_2)\} \\
&= \min\left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u_1), \tilde{\zeta}_M(u_2)\}, \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(a_1), \tilde{\zeta}_M(a_2)\}, \min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(v_1), \tilde{\zeta}_M(v_2)\}\right\} \\
&= \min\left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(u_1), \tilde{\delta}_M(a_1), \tilde{\delta}_M(v_1)\}, \min\{\tilde{\zeta}_M(u_2), \tilde{\zeta}_M(a_2), \tilde{\zeta}_M(v_2)\}\right\} \\
&\leq \min\left\{\inf_{f_1 \in u_1 a_1 v_1} \tilde{\delta}_M(f_1), \inf_{f_2 \in u_2 a_2 v_2} \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_2)\right\} \\
&\leq \inf_{\substack{f_1 \in u_1 a_1 v_1, \\ f_2 \in u_2 a_2 v_2}} \left\{\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M(f_1), \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_2)\}\right\} \\
&\leq \inf_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1 a_1 v_1, u_2 a_2 v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_1, f_2) \\
&\leq \inf_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_1, f_2) \text{ and} \\
& \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u_1, u_2), \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(a_1, a_2), \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v_1, v_2)\} \\
&= \max\left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u_2)\}, \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(a_2)\}, \max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v_2)\}\right\} \\
&= \max\left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(u_1), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(a_1), \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(v_1)\}, \max\{\tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u_2), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(a_2), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v_2)\}\right\} \\
&\geq \max\left\{\sup_{f_1 \in u_1 a_1 v_1} \tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f_1), \sup_{f_2 \in u_2 a_2 v_2} \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_2)\right\} \\
&\geq \sup_{\substack{f_1 \in u_1 a_1 v_1, \\ f_2 \in u_2 a_2 v_2}} \left\{\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM}(f_1), \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_2)\}\right\} \\
&\geq \sup_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1 a_1 v_1, u_2 a_2 v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_1, f_2) \\
&\geq \sup_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_1, f_2)
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$ is an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideal of $\mathcal{T}^* \times \mathcal{T}^*$. \square

Theorem 5.2. *Let \mathcal{T}^* be a hypersemigroup. If the interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy sets $\mathcal{P} = \langle \tilde{\delta}_M, \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \rangle$ and $\mathcal{Q} = \langle \tilde{\zeta}_M, \tilde{\zeta}_{NM} \rangle$ are interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals of \mathcal{T}^* then the $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\beta})$ -level set of $\mathcal{P} \times \mathcal{Q}$ is also an interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideal of $\mathcal{T}^* \times \mathcal{T}^*$.*

Proof. Let $(u_1, u_2), (v_1, v_2), (f_1, f_2) \in \mathcal{T}^* \times \mathcal{T}^*$ such that $(u_1, u_2), (v_1, v_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M)^{\tilde{\alpha}}$. Which implies that $\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(u_1, u_2) \geq \tilde{\alpha}$ and

$\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(v_1, v_2) \geq \tilde{\alpha}$.
 Since $\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(u_1, u_2), \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(v_1, v_2)\} \leq \inf_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_1, f_2)$
 $\implies \inf_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_1, f_2) \geq \min\{\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\alpha}\} \geq \tilde{\alpha}$
 $\implies \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_1, f_2) \geq \tilde{\alpha}$ for $(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2)$
 $\implies (f_1, f_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M)^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ for $(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2)$
 $\implies (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M)^{\tilde{\alpha}}$. Hence $(\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M)^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ is a subsemihypergroup of \mathcal{T}^* .

Now let $(u_1, u_2), (v_1, v_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM})^{\tilde{\beta}}$. Which implies that $\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u_1, u_2) \leq \tilde{\beta}$ and $\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v_1, v_2) \leq \tilde{\beta}$. Since
 $\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u_1, u_2), \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v_1, v_2)\} \geq \sup_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_1, f_2)$
 $\implies \sup_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_1, f_2) \leq \max\{\tilde{\beta}, \tilde{\beta}\} \leq \tilde{\beta}$
 $\implies \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_1, f_2) \leq \tilde{\beta}$ for $(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2)$
 $\implies (f_1, f_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM})^{\tilde{\beta}}$ for $(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2)$
 $\implies (u_1, u_2)(v_1, v_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM})^{\tilde{\beta}}$. Hence $(\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM})^{\tilde{\beta}}$ is a subsemihypergroup.

Let $(u_1, u_2), (v_1, v_2), (a_1, a_2), (f_1, f_2) \in \mathcal{T}^* \times \mathcal{T}^*$ such that $(u_1, u_2), (v_1, v_2), (a_1, a_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M)^{\tilde{\alpha}}$. Which implies that $\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(u_1, u_2) \geq \tilde{\alpha}$, $\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(a_1, a_2) \geq \tilde{\alpha}$ and $\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(v_1, v_2) \geq \tilde{\alpha}$. Since
 $\min\{\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(u_1, u_2), \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(a_1, a_2), \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(v_1, v_2)\}$
 $\leq \inf_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_1, f_2)$
 $\implies \inf_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_1, f_2) \geq \min\{\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{\alpha}\} \geq \tilde{\alpha}$
 $\implies \tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M(f_1, f_2) \geq \tilde{\alpha}$ for $(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2)$
 $\implies (f_1, f_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M)^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ for $(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2)$
 $\implies (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M)^{\tilde{\alpha}}$. Hence $(\tilde{\delta}_M \times \tilde{\zeta}_M)^{\tilde{\alpha}}$ is a weak bi-hyperideal.

Let $(u_1, u_2), (v_1, v_2), (a_1, a_2), (f_1, f_2) \in \mathcal{T}^* \times \mathcal{T}^*$ such that $(u_1, u_2), (v_1, v_2), (a_1, a_2) \in \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}^{\tilde{\beta}}$. Which implies that $\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u_1, u_2) \leq \tilde{\beta}$, $\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(a_1, a_2) \leq \tilde{\beta}$ and $\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v_1, v_2) \leq \tilde{\beta}$. Since
 $\max\{\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(u_1, u_2), \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(a_1, a_2), \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(v_1, v_2)\}$
 $\geq \sup_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_1, f_2)$
 $\implies \sup_{(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2)} \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_1, f_2) \leq \max\{\tilde{\beta}, \tilde{\beta}\} \leq \tilde{\beta}$
 $\implies \tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM}(f_1, f_2) \leq \tilde{\beta}$ for $(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2)$
 $\implies (f_1, f_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM})^{\tilde{\beta}}$ for $(f_1, f_2) \in (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2)$
 $\implies (u_1, u_2)(a_1, a_2)(v_1, v_2) \in (\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM})^{\tilde{\beta}}$. Hence $(\tilde{\delta}_{NM} \times \tilde{\zeta}_{NM})^{\tilde{\beta}}$ is a weak bi-hyperideal. □

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented the notion of interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy subsemihypergroup and interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals in hypersemigroups.

We characterized cartesian product of interval-valued Pythagorean fuzzy weak bi-hyperideals. We investigated some properties with suitable examples. In continuity of this paper, we study interval-valued weak bi Γ -hyperideals in Γ -hypersemigroups.

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